

Adopting European CORINE Land Cover Concept in Bangladesh: Environmental Assessment

Md. Mizanur Rahman

Information and Communication Technology Division, Bangladesh, E-mail:

rahmanboku@gmail.com

Abstract

Corine Land Cover (CLC) provides comparable digital maps of land use patterns, which is useful for nature conservation and environmental analysis. The component of the CLC aims to gather information relating to the environment on certain priority topics like human disturbances, land use patterns, naturalness, etc. The overall objective of the study was to examine the suitability of the adoption of CLC in Bangladesh and to draw a map considering Bangladesh's perspectives. Empirical data were collected from focus group discussions and key informant interviews. Based on the respondents' perceptions, a CLC for Bangladesh was developed which described 44 classes of land cover organized hierarchically in three levels. The first level defined the land pattern. The second level corresponded to the physical and physiognomic entities in detail; finally, level 3 was composed of acutely defined 44 classes. This map will help to assess the naturalness and land use pattern in Bangladesh.

Keywords: European, Corine Land Cover, naturalness, land classes, policy interventions, human disturbances

Introduction

Corine Land Cover (CLC) is a database of geographic land cover encompassing most of the European countries. It is based on the interpretation of satellite images. Images acquired by earth observation satellites are used to derive land cover information. It provides comparable digital maps of land use patterns (Büttner *et al.* 2004). This is useful for nature conservation and environmental analysis. The component of the CLC aims to gather information relating to the environment on certain priority topics like human disturbances, land use patterns, naturalness, etc. CLC covers all activities related to satellite image acquisition, ortho-rectification and production of local, national and continental mosaic, and temporal variation of images. CLC provides an inventory of the earth's surface features for managing the environment (Bielecka & Jenerowicz 2019).

The EU established CLC in 1985 to create pan-European databases on land cover, biotopes (habitats) and soil maps (Cornaert 2004). An updated CLC database was launched in January 2000. CLC describes 44 classes of land cover organized hierarchically in three levels. The first level (5 classes) defines the land pattern (artificial areas, agricultural land, forests and semi-natural areas, wetlands, and water surfaces). The second level (15 classes) corresponds to the physical and physiognomic entities in detail (urban zones, forests, lakes, etc.); finally, level 3 is composed of acutely defined 44 classes (residential areas, airports, commercial areas, etc.) (Yilmaz 2010). Environmental protection has become a major challenge and concern for the whole world. The updated information on the land cover has become important for environmental assessment. The growing interest in such information indicates the importance of CLC. The study aimed to assess the suitability of the adoption of this concept in Bangladesh.

Methodology

Empirical data was used for this study. A focus group discussion was done incorporating the respondents from diverse stakeholders. A total number of 10 key respondents were interviewed to a set of parameters. Content analysis was done to organize the land cover hierarchically in different levels and classes to draw a map of Bangladesh.

How to adopt in Bangladesh?

At the outset, different levels and classes of land cover need to be categorized based on the practical scenarios of Bangladesh. Together with a methodology to implement the CLC concept in Bangladesh should be developed. Rapid landscape changes are occurring in Bangladesh. CLC is essential not only in research but also in environmental management. Harmonized and standardized spatial reference data are considered obligatory in support of environmental management. It is also essential for development, territorial impact assessment, regional planning, nature conservation, environmental protection, integrated coastal management and strategic environmental assessment.

Based on the respondents' perceptions, a CLC for Bangladesh was developed which described 44 classes of land cover organized hierarchically in three levels. The first level defined the land pattern. The second level corresponded to the physical and physiognomic entities in detail; finally, level 3 was composed of acutely defined 44 classes (Figure 1). This map will help to assess the naturalness (hemeroby) in Bangladesh (Rahman 2023).

Land use/land-cover change is the most important factor in causing biodiversity loss. Temporal significant increase or decrease in forest cover can be measured through CLC. It provides important information, which is useful for conservation planning. An increasing conservation effort should be made to protect the forests and semi-natural areas in Bangladesh. Moreover, future conservation efforts should consider the broad socio-political and ecological processes that are most likely to occur across the coastal areas. The network of protected areas should be functionally integrated into a conservation strategy.

CLC shows the land cover change in ecosystems such as forests, lakes, agricultural activities and vegetation, and the impact of human activities (such as urbanization, industrialization, food production, transport etc.) on land. The database also serves a wide range of application sectors. Environmental applications focus in their majority on nature conservation, biodiversity-related issues, water and soil management, air pollution and climate change. CLC is a planner's tool and provides land cover information that helps policy makers to visualise the area of interest. It can be

used as an analytical tool supplying statistics about land use or the development of land use and management in a specific area.

Figure 1: A CLC for was developed for Bangladesh based on respondents' perceptions

The main objective of CLC is to develop a core set of indicators to provide policy-relevant information on the terrestrial environment, to review and evaluate the effectiveness of existing policies, and to provide the basis for better integration between environmental and sectoral policies. It can support the development of environmental indicators for nature conservation. For example, it is possible to show where an endangered habitat is under intense pressure from factors such as transport, urban expansion or agriculture.

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